

GAMMA-FACTOR PARITY AND POLE REMOVAL IN SMOOTH ZERO-COUNTING CONSTANTS FOR ZETA, BETA, AND THE GAUSSIAN NUMBER FIELD

MUSTAFA YILIK

Independent Researcher, Nuremberg, Germany

ORCID: 0009-0003-8332-5336

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ABSTRACT. We fix a single upper-half zero-counting convention and compute the additive constants in the smooth main terms of the completed Riemann zeta function $\xi(s)$, the completed Dirichlet beta function $\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$, and the completed Dedekind zeta function of $\mathbb{Q}(i)$. The constants separate into two algebraic sources: the gamma-factor parity, determined by $\chi(-1)$, and the pole-removing factor.

For a primitive Dirichlet character χ the gamma-and-pole contribution is $c_\chi = -\chi(-1)/8 + \delta_{\chi, \text{prin}}$, where $\delta_{\chi, \text{prin}} = 1$ only for the principal primitive character. For a number field with r_1 real places the archimedean-and-pole constant is $C_K = 1 - r_1/8$. Specializing gives the zeta smooth constant $7/8$ and the beta smooth constant $1/8$. In the product factorization $\zeta_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}(s) = \zeta(s)\beta(s)$ the gamma-factor contributions $-1/8$ and $+1/8$ cancel; the zeta pole-removing contribution survives, yielding constant 1 for the Gaussian field. This normalization fixes the additive baseline for finite-interval residual analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Riemann–von Mangoldt formula provides the model case. It counts the nontrivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function up to height T , and under the upper-half convention used here its smooth part is

$$\frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{T}{2\pi e} + \frac{7}{8}.$$

The L -function $L(s, \chi_{-4})$ attached to the primitive odd character modulo 4, which we write $\beta(s)$, has the corresponding smooth additive constant $1/8$. Comparing these two constants separates two effects that are combined in the usual main terms: the parity $\chi(-1)$ of the underlying character determines whether the gamma factor is even or odd, which fixes the sign of

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the gamma-factor contribution, while the pole-removing factor appears only for zeta.

Result (constant decomposition). This paper fixes one upper-half zero-counting convention and computes the constant term contributed by each local factor of the completed functions: the even real gamma factor, the odd real gamma factor, the complex archimedean factor, and the pole-removing factor. For zeta and beta, assembling these per-factor contributions gives

$$c_\zeta = -\frac{1}{8} + 1 = \frac{7}{8}, \quad c_\beta = \frac{1}{8} + 0 = \frac{1}{8},$$

while the general primitive-Dirichlet and number-field contributions are

$$c_\chi = -\frac{\chi(-1)}{8} + \delta_{\chi,\text{prin}}, \quad C_K = 1 - \frac{r_1}{8}.$$

Here c_χ is the gamma-and-pole contribution for a primitive Dirichlet character χ , with $\delta_{\chi,\text{prin}} = 1$ only for the trivial conductor-1 character, and C_K is the archimedean-and-pole contribution for a number field with r_1 real places. Thus the principal primitive character gives $7/8$, a nonprincipal even character gives $-1/8$, and a nonprincipal odd character gives $1/8$; for a number field, each real place contributes $-1/8$, each complex place contributes no constant, and the pole-removing factor contributes $+1$.

For the Gaussian field, the Dirichlet and Dedekind descriptions meet through the product factorization

$$\zeta_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}(s) = \zeta(s)\beta(s).$$

The zeta and beta gamma-factor constants cancel, while the pole-removing contribution remains:

$$c_\zeta + c_\beta = \underbrace{\left(-\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{8}\right)}_{\text{gamma}} + \underbrace{(1 + 0)}_{\text{pole}} = 1.$$

The Dedekind completion gives the same constant because $\mathbb{Q}(i)$ has signature $(r_1, r_2) = (0, 1)$, hence $C_K = 1$.

The separation into a gamma-factor term and a pole-removing term depends on how the completed function is written. The total additive constant is fixed by the zero-counting convention, whereas the allocation of that constant among the factors can change under an equivalent completion; Section 3 records this point explicitly for zeta. The cancellation $-1/8 + 1/8 = 0$ in the Gaussian product is independent of this allocation, since both factors carry their standard gamma factors.

The individual smooth main terms are classical: the zeta term belongs to Riemann [10] and von Mangoldt, the Dirichlet L -function term is the upper-half specialization of the main term of Bennett et al. [1, Section 2], and the Dedekind term follows from a standard contour argument for the completed Dedekind zeta function. Since the additive constant does not affect the order of growth of the zero count, it is naturally carried inside

the $O(\log T)$ error term, and it becomes relevant only once the residual itself is compared across functions. We claim no new zero-counting estimate. The contribution of this paper is a normalization: under a single upper-half convention we record these constants exactly, and uniformly, for ζ , β , and $\zeta_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}$.

The same normalization fixes the additive origin for finite-interval residuals. If a zero-counting function is compared with a smooth main term on an interval, then changing only the additive constant shifts the corresponding finite-interval Fourier integral by an explicit endpoint term. Section 5 records this consequence. This normalization underlies subsequent work by the author.

Outline. Section 2 fixes the upper-half counting convention and the completed functions, and records the argument-principle contour and the right-half argument identity. Section 3 computes the gamma-factor and pole-removing constants for a general primitive Dirichlet L -function and specializes them to the zeta and beta functions. Section 4 records the number-field archimedean-and-pole constant, compares the product and Dedekind routes for $\mathbb{Q}(i)$, and presents the four-row constant table. Section 5 records the finite-interval consequence of changing the additive constant.

2. CONVENTIONS AND THE ARGUMENT PRINCIPLE

This section fixes the upper-half zero-counting convention and derives the right-half argument identity used below. We construct the rectangular contour and apply Cauchy's argument principle. We then use the functional equations of the completed functions to reduce the full rectangle to a right-half identity. All logarithms are natural logarithms.

2.1. Zero-counting convention and pathwise argument. We use one zero-counting convention throughout the paper. Let F denote the completed Riemann zeta function or the completed Dirichlet beta function (defined below). We define

$$N_F(T) = \#\{\rho : F(\rho) = 0, 0 < \operatorname{Re} \rho < 1, 0 < \operatorname{Im} \rho \leq T\},$$

counting multiplicity. A positive height T is called admissible for F if $F(\rho) = 0$ implies $\operatorname{Im} \rho \neq T$. We first make direct contour arguments at admissible heights. At zero ordinates we use the right-continuous convention

$$N_F(T) = \lim_{\varepsilon \downarrow 0} N_F(T + \varepsilon).$$

Pathwise argument. For a piecewise smooth oriented path P on which F has no zeros, write

$$\Delta_P \arg F = \operatorname{Im} \int_P \frac{F'(s)}{F(s)} ds.$$

Equivalently, we choose a continuous branch of $\log F$ along the zero-free path P and take the net change of its imaginary part. The argument is

used pathwise throughout: the branch is fixed only after the contour and its starting value have been specified, and it is then continued continuously along that zero-free path.

2.2. Full-rectangle count. We first count the zeros using a wide rectangular contour. For the two completed functions treated here, all zeros inside the wide rectangle lie in the critical strip. They are entire and possess the functional equation described below. After the usual cancellations, their zeros inside the following rectangle are exactly the nontrivial zeros with $0 < \operatorname{Re} s < 1$ [13, 2]. Equivalently, there are no completed-function zeros in the closed right region $1 \leq \operatorname{Re} s \leq 2$ or in the reflected closed left region $-1 \leq \operatorname{Re} s \leq 0$. On the right this is supplied by the standard nonvanishing of $\zeta(s)$ and primitive Dirichlet L -functions on and to the right of $\operatorname{Re} s = 1$, together with the cancellation of the zeta pole in ξ ; the left statement is obtained from the functional equations [2, 6]. This nonvanishing holds for all heights. The trivial zeros and the pole at $s = 1$ for ζ are already canceled by the completed factors used here.

Lemma 2.1 (Full-rectangle count). *Let F be either $\xi(s)$ or $\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$ (defined below). Let $0 < \eta < T$, and suppose that F has no zeros on the boundary of the positively oriented rectangle*

$$\mathcal{R}_{\eta, T} : 2 + i\eta \rightarrow 2 + iT \rightarrow -1 + iT \rightarrow -1 + i\eta \rightarrow 2 + i\eta.$$

Define

$$N_F(\eta, T) = \#\{\rho : F(\rho) = 0, 0 < \operatorname{Re} \rho < 1, \eta < \operatorname{Im} \rho < T\},$$

counting multiplicity. Then

$$N_F(\eta, T) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \Delta_{\mathcal{R}_{\eta, T}} \arg F.$$

Proof. Because F is entire and has no zeros on $\partial\mathcal{R}_{\eta, T}$, the function F'/F is meromorphic inside $\mathcal{R}_{\eta, T}$, with a pole at each zero of F whose residue equals the multiplicity. Cauchy's argument principle gives

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\mathcal{R}_{\eta, T}} \frac{F'(s)}{F(s)} ds = \#\{\rho : F(\rho) = 0, \rho \in \operatorname{int} \mathcal{R}_{\eta, T}\}.$$

Taking imaginary parts yields the stated argument variation. By the zero-location facts recalled above, the completed functions have no zeros in the closed regions $1 \leq \operatorname{Re} s \leq 2$ and $-1 \leq \operatorname{Re} s \leq 0$ along the portion of the rectangle being counted. Thus the wide-rectangle count is exactly $N_F(\eta, T)$. Letting $\eta \downarrow 0$ and then using right-continuity gives the paper's convention for $N_F(T)$. The half-contours do not enter this counting lemma; they are introduced as a symmetry reduction only after the full rectangle has supplied the count. \square

2.3. Completed functions and symmetry reduction. To relate the argument variation on the left half of the rectangle to the right half, we need functions that are symmetric with respect to the critical line.

The completed Riemann zeta function is

$$\xi(s) = \frac{1}{2} s(s-1) \pi^{-s/2} \Gamma(s/2) \zeta(s).$$

The factor $\frac{1}{2} s(s-1)$ cancels the simple pole of $\zeta(s)$ at $s = 1$, making $\xi(s)$ entire and of order one.

For the Dirichlet beta function we need the primitive odd character modulo 4, equivalently the Kronecker symbol $\left(\frac{-4}{\cdot}\right)$,

$$\chi_{-4}(n) = \begin{cases} 0, & n \equiv 0, 2 \pmod{4}, \\ 1, & n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, \\ -1, & n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

Its conductor is 4 and its parity is odd. The completed beta function is

$$\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4}) = \left(\frac{4}{\pi}\right)^{(s+1)/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{s+1}{2}\right) \beta(s).$$

Both completed functions satisfy conjugation symmetry $F(\bar{s}) = \overline{F(s)}$ and the root-number-one functional equation $F(s) = F(1-s)$. For ξ this is classical. For $\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$ the Gauss sum is $\tau(\chi_{-4}) = \sum_{n \pmod{4}} \chi_{-4}(n) e^{2\pi i n/4} = 2i$, the parity is $a = 1$, and the conductor is $q = 4$, so the root number is $\tau(\chi_{-4}) / (i^a \sqrt{q}) = 2i / (i \cdot 2) = 1$, verifying the normalization.

Combining conjugation symmetry and the functional equation gives the relation we shall use in the reflection lemma, where the bar again denotes complex conjugation:

$$F(s) = \overline{F(1-\bar{s})}.$$

We split the full rectangle by the critical-line segment from $1/2 + i\eta$ to $1/2 + iT$. If this segment meets zeros of F , we replace it by pairwise disjoint small semicircular arcs around those zeros, lying inside the full rectangle and avoiding all other zeros. This yields a zero-free detoured path $C_{\eta, T}^{\det}$. The same detoured path is used as the internal boundary of both half-contours, with opposite orientations. Because the integrand F'/F at a point s on the critical line is sent by the reflection $s \mapsto 1 - \bar{s}$ to its conjugate on the reflected path, and because the detoured path runs in opposite directions on the two halves, the argument variation along it cancels exactly when the halves are recombined. Figure 1 depicts this convention.

Lemma 2.2 (Functional symmetry). *Let F be either $\xi(s)$ or $\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$. Under the hypotheses of Lemma 2.1, split $\mathcal{R}_{\eta, T}$ by the segment from $1/2 + i\eta$ to $1/2 + iT$, or by the shared detoured path $C_{\eta, T}^{\det}$ if the segment meets zeros of F . Then*

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{R}_{\eta, T}} \arg F = 2(\Delta_{R_{\eta, T}^+} \arg F + \Delta_{T^+} \arg F + \Delta_{B_{\eta}^+} \arg F),$$

FIGURE 1. The wide rectangle (solid right edge, dashed left edge) supplies the zero count via Cauchy's argument principle. Under the combined symmetry $F(s) = \overline{F(1 - \bar{s})}$ and the reflection $J(s) = 1 - \bar{s}$, the dashed-and-hatched left half is absorbed into the right half (solid arrows); shared detours around critical-line zeros cancel when the halves are recombined.

where

$$R_{\eta,T}^+ : 2 + i\eta \rightarrow 2 + iT, \quad T_T^+ : 2 + iT \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} + iT, \quad B_\eta^+ : \frac{1}{2} + i\eta \rightarrow 2 + i\eta.$$

Consequently,

$$N_F(\eta, T) = \frac{1}{\pi} (\Delta_{R_{\eta,T}^+} \arg F + \Delta_{T_T^+} \arg F + \Delta_{B_\eta^+} \arg F).$$

Proof. The proof compares the left and right half-contours by reflection; the shared internal path cancels because it is traversed in opposite directions. Let $J(s) = 1 - \bar{s}$. The identity $F(s) = \overline{F(J(s))}$ implies that, for each zero-free oriented path P in the left half,

$$\Delta_P \arg F = -\Delta_{J(P)} \arg F,$$

where $J(P)$ carries the induced orientation. Two sign reversals enter here, and must be kept apart. First, conjugation gives the identity $\Delta_P \arg F = -\Delta_{J(P)} \arg F$ stated above. Second, $J(s) = 1 - \bar{s}$ is a reflection across $\text{Re } s = 1/2$, and is therefore orientation-reversing: it carries each left edge to the matching right edge traversed in the opposite direction. For the top edge, J sends $\frac{1}{2} + iT \rightarrow -1 + iT$ to $\frac{1}{2} + iT \rightarrow 2 + iT$, that is, to $-T_T^+$; hence

$$\Delta_{\text{left top}} \arg F = -\Delta_{-T_T^+} \arg F = \Delta_{T_T^+} \arg F,$$

and the left vertical and left bottom edges give $\Delta_{R_{\eta,T}^+}$ and $\Delta_{B_\eta^+}$ in the same way. The two reversals compose to a plus sign; a single reversal would give cancellation rather than the factor 2. Adding the reflected-left edges to the right edges doubles $\Delta_{R_{\eta,T}^+} + \Delta_{T_T^+} + \Delta_{B_\eta^+}$, while the shared internal path (or

detour) cancels by additivity, being traversed in opposite directions by the two halves; this is the factor 2. Combining with Lemma 2.1 gives the final formula. \square

2.4. Lower edge and right-half identity. It remains to justify the lower edge in the limit $\eta \downarrow 0$. This is a local branch statement near the positive real axis.

Lemma 2.3 (Lower-edge contribution). *Let F be either $\xi(s)$ or $\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$. Choose the local branch of $\arg F$ near the interval $[1/2, 2]$ so that*

$$\arg F(x) = 0 \quad (1/2 \leq x \leq 2).$$

Then

$$\lim_{\eta \downarrow 0} \Delta_{B_\eta^+} \arg F = 0.$$

Proof. We verify that $F(x) > 0$ on $1/2 \leq x \leq 2$ for both completed functions. For $\xi(x)$, the factors $\pi^{-x/2}$ and $\Gamma(x/2)$ are positive [9, Equation (5.2.1)]. For $1 < x \leq 2$, both $x(x-1)$ and $\zeta(x)$ are positive. For $1/2 \leq x < 1$, the factor $x(x-1)$ is negative, and we need $\zeta(x) < 0$. Write η_D for the Dirichlet eta function, with the subscript D serving only to distinguish it from the contour height η :

$$\eta_D(x) = \sum_{n \geq 1} (-1)^{n-1} n^{-x}.$$

It satisfies $\zeta(x) = \eta_D(x)/(1 - 2^{1-x})$. For $x > 0$ the alternating series has monotonically decreasing terms, so $\eta_D(x) > 0$ by the alternating series test. Since $1 - 2^{1-x} < 0$ for $0 < x < 1$, we obtain $\zeta(x) < 0$ [2]. At $x = 1$, the simple pole of $\zeta(s)$ is canceled analytically by the factor $(s-1)$ in $\xi(s)$: we have $\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} (s-1)\zeta(s) = 1$, and the remaining factors $\pi^{-s/2}$, $\Gamma(s/2)$, and $\frac{1}{2}s$ are all positive, so $\xi(1) > 0$.

For $\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$, the conductor factor and gamma factor are positive on $[1/2, 2]$. Moreover

$$\beta(x) = 1 - 3^{-x} + 5^{-x} - 7^{-x} + \dots$$

is a positive alternating series for $x > 0$. Hence $\Lambda(x, \chi_{-4}) > 0$ on $[1/2, 2]$.

By continuity and compactness, for every $\epsilon > 0$ there is $\delta > 0$ such that, if $0 < \eta < \delta$ and $1/2 \leq x \leq 2$, then $F(x + i\eta)$ lies in the sector $|\arg z| < \epsilon$ around the positive real axis, using the local branch fixed above. Therefore

$$|\Delta_{B_\eta^+} \arg F| = |\arg F(2 + i\eta) - \arg F(\frac{1}{2} + i\eta)| \leq 2\epsilon.$$

Since ϵ is arbitrary, the lower-edge contribution tends to zero. \square

Combining the three lemmas gives the right-half argument identity used in the next section. The full rectangle supplies the count via Cauchy's argument principle; the half-rectangle is its symmetry reduction.

Corollary 2.4 (Right-half identity). *Let F be either $\xi(s)$ or $\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$, and let T be admissible. Use the lower-edge branch normalization from Lemma 2.3 and the shared detour convention from Lemma 2.2. With*

$$P_{0,T}^+ : 2 \rightarrow 2 + iT \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} + iT,$$

and with the argument continued from $\arg F(2) = 0$ along this path,

$$N_F(T) = \frac{1}{\pi} \Delta_{P_{0,T}^+} \arg F.$$

At zero ordinates, use the right-continuous convention from the definition of $N_F(T)$.

Proof. Apply Lemma 2.2 for $\eta > 0$. Lemma 2.3 gives $\Delta_{B_\eta^+} \arg F \rightarrow 0$ as $\eta \downarrow 0$ under the stated branch normalization. The right vertical segment $2 + i\eta \rightarrow 2 + iT$ is zero-free, and the short segment $2 \rightarrow 2 + i\eta$ contributes vanishing argument variation in the same limit. Hence the remaining limiting path is $2 \rightarrow 2 + iT \rightarrow 1/2 + iT$, with argument continued from $\arg F(2) = 0$. The value at a zero ordinate is then obtained by right-continuity. \square

If zeros lie on the inserted critical-line path, the shared detour convention does not assign such zeros to one half-contour separately. Their multiplicities are counted by the full rectangle in Lemma 2.1; the inserted detoured path cancels only after the two halves are recombined. The right-half identity is therefore a limiting branch-variation identity obtained after that full-rectangle count.

In the next section we expand the completed functions at $s = 1/2 + iT$. The right-half identity then separates the gamma-conductor argument, the argument of the zeta pole-removing factor, and the argument of the underlying L -function. For the beta function the analytic argument term is

$$S_\beta(T) = \frac{1}{\pi} \arg \beta \left(\frac{1}{2} + iT \right),$$

where the argument is continued along the path $P_{0,T}^+$ from Corollary 2.4.

The contour reduction supplies the branch-variation identity used in the smooth constant calculation.

3. GAMMA FACTORS AND THE POLE-REMOVING FACTOR

Having established the contour integral and the right-half argument identity in Section 2, we now evaluate its asymptotic expansion. In this section we isolate the two separate algebraic sources of the smooth counting formula: the gamma factor, whose contribution is fixed in sign by the parity $\chi(-1)$ of the underlying character, and the pole-removing factor. We begin with the Stirling approximation, then treat the gamma and pole terms separately before combining them. The even and odd real gamma rows and the pole-removing row of Table 1 are obtained in this section; the complex archimedean row, which contributes zero, is supplied in Section 4.

Throughout this section

$$s = \frac{1}{2} + iT, \quad T > 0,$$

and arguments are continued using the branch convention inherited from Corollary 2.4.

Let $q > 0$ be the conductor and $a \in \{0, 1\}$ the index of the gamma factor, with $a = 0$ for the even factor $\Gamma(s/2)$ and $a = 1$ for the odd factor $\Gamma((s+1)/2)$; for a primitive Dirichlet character this is the parity, in the sense $\chi(-1) = (-1)^a$. Define the gamma-conductor factor

$$G_{q,a}(s) = \left(\frac{q}{\pi}\right)^{(s+a)/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{s+a}{2}\right),$$

and set

$$\sigma_a = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{a}{2}.$$

Then on the critical line

$$\frac{s+a}{2} = \sigma_a + \frac{iT}{2}.$$

For the zeta gamma factor we use $q = 1$ and $a = 0$. For beta, with the primitive character χ_{-4} , we use $q = 4$ and $a = 1$. We record separately a quantity c_{pole} , the contribution after division by π of an explicit pole-removing factor. In this paper

$$c_{\text{pole}}(\zeta) = 1, \quad c_{\text{pole}}(\beta) = 0.$$

We first approximate the argument of the gamma-conductor factor using the Stirling expansion.

Lemma 3.1 (Stirling argument term). *For fixed real σ and $y \rightarrow +\infty$, on the continuous branch compatible with the upper-half argument convention,*

$$\arg \Gamma(\sigma + iy) = y \log y - y + \left(\sigma - \frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{\pi}{2} + O(y^{-1}).$$

Proof. This is the imaginary part of Stirling's expansion for $\log \Gamma(z)$ in a sector away from the negative real axis [9, Equation (5.11.1)]. The branch is the one reached by continuous continuation along the Section 2 path. The $O(y^{-1})$ term is the Stirling truncation error for the gamma factor. \square

Define

$$\Theta_{q,a}(T) = \arg G_{q,a}\left(\frac{1}{2} + iT\right).$$

For $q = 1$ and $a = 0$ this is the classical Riemann–Siegel θ -function [13, Section 4.17]; for general (q, a) it is the argument of the gamma-conductor factor of a completed Dirichlet L -function.

With the Stirling approximation established, we extract the constant term from the argument variation to isolate the gamma-factor contribution.

Proposition 3.2 (Gamma-factor contribution). *Let $q > 0$ and $a \in \{0, 1\}$, and let*

$$G_{q,a}(s) = \left(\frac{q}{\pi}\right)^{(s+a)/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{s+a}{2}\right).$$

With $\Theta_{q,a}(T) = \arg G_{q,a}\left(\frac{1}{2} + iT\right)$, the gamma-conductor contribution satisfies

$$\frac{\Theta_{q,a}(T)}{\pi} = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{qT}{2\pi e} + \frac{2a-1}{8} + O(T^{-1}),$$

where the $O(T^{-1})$ term is the Stirling truncation from Lemma 3.1. Hence the associated smooth main expression obtained by dropping only this Stirling truncation is

$$\frac{\Theta_{q,a}^{\text{main}}(T)}{\pi} = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{qT}{2\pi e} + \frac{2a-1}{8}.$$

The constant $(2a-1)/8$ is the gamma-factor contribution; the conductor enters only the logarithmic term.

Proof. On the critical line,

$$G_{q,a}\left(\frac{1}{2} + iT\right) = \left(\frac{q}{\pi}\right)^{\sigma_a + iT/2} \Gamma\left(\sigma_a + \frac{iT}{2}\right).$$

Since q/π is positive real,

$$\arg\left(\frac{q}{\pi}\right)^{\sigma_a + iT/2} = \frac{T}{2} \log \frac{q}{\pi}.$$

By Lemma 3.1, with $y = T/2$,

$$\arg \Gamma\left(\sigma_a + \frac{iT}{2}\right) = \frac{T}{2} \log \frac{T}{2} - \frac{T}{2} + \left(\sigma_a - \frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{\pi}{2} + O(T^{-1}).$$

Adding the conductor and gamma contributions gives

$$\Theta_{q,a}(T) = \frac{T}{2} \log \frac{qT}{2\pi} - \frac{T}{2} + \left(\sigma_a - \frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{\pi}{2} + O(T^{-1}).$$

Since

$$\sigma_a - \frac{1}{2} = \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{a}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{2} = \frac{2a-1}{4},$$

division by π gives the stated formula. Dropping the displayed Stirling truncation defines the smooth main expression. \square

The completed zeta function contains an explicit pole-removing factor; we evaluate its argument contribution strictly under the upper-half branch normalization.

Lemma 3.3 (Zeta pole-removing factor). *For $s = 1/2 + iT$ with $T > 0$,*

$$\frac{1}{2} s(s-1) = -\frac{1}{8} - \frac{T^2}{2} < 0.$$

Under the Section 2 branch convention, this factor is reached from the upper half-plane and has argument $+\pi$ at $s = 1/2 + iT$:

$$\arg\left(\frac{1}{2}s(s-1)\right) = \pi.$$

Therefore its contribution after division by π is

$$c_{\text{pole}}(\zeta) = 1.$$

Proof. Multiplying gives

$$\left(\frac{1}{2} + iT\right) \left(-\frac{1}{2} + iT\right) = -\frac{1}{4} - T^2,$$

and division by 2 gives the displayed negative real number. Along the Section 2 path, the factor $\frac{1}{2}s(s-1)$ approaches this negative real value from the upper half-plane: on the vertical segment $s = 2 + it$ its imaginary part is positive for $t > 0$, and on the horizontal segment $s = x + iT$ its imaginary part is $T(2x-1)/2$, which decreases to 0 as $x \downarrow 1/2$. Hence the continuous argument at the endpoint is $+\pi$, not $-\pi$. This is the pole-removing row of Table 1 in the zeta case. \square

Remark 3.4 (Display of the pole-removing factor). The separation above is a choice in how the completed zeta factor is displayed, not a change of the completed function. Indeed,

$$\frac{1}{2}s(s-1)\pi^{-s/2}\Gamma(s/2)\zeta(s) = (s-1)\pi^{-s/2}\Gamma(s/2+1)\zeta(s),$$

so the factor s may be absorbed into the gamma factor. In that presentation part of the constant is carried by the shifted gamma term and part by the remaining pole-removing factor. We keep $\frac{1}{2}s(s-1)$ explicit because it isolates the pole-removing contribution as the +1 row in Table 1; the total zero-counting constant is unchanged.

Having evaluated the gamma and pole contributions independently, we combine them to justify the corresponding rows of the decomposition table.

Proposition 3.5 (Real gamma and pole rows). *Under the upper-half convention fixed in Section 2, the even real gamma, odd real gamma, and pole-removing rows of Table 1 have constants $-1/8$, $+1/8$, and $+1$, respectively. The complex archimedean row is supplied by the complex-place calculation in Proposition 4.1.*

Proof. The even and odd gamma rows are Proposition 3.2 with $a = 0$ and $a = 1$, respectively. The pole row is Lemma 3.3. These rows are contributions: they record the constant term in the smooth argument contribution under the path convention already fixed. \square

The next proposition packages these contributions in the form used for primitive Dirichlet characters.

Proposition 3.6 (Smooth constant decomposition). *Let $q > 0$, let $a \in \{0, 1\}$, and let c_{pole} denote the contribution after division by π of an explicit pole-removing factor. The smooth upper-half main expression extracted from the gamma-conductor factor and an explicit pole-removing factor has constant*

$$C(q, a, c_{\text{pole}}) = \frac{2a - 1}{8} + c_{\text{pole}}.$$

The first term is the gamma-factor contribution, and the second term is the pole-removing contribution.

Proof. Proposition 3.2 gives the gamma-conductor main contribution

$$\frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{qT}{2\pi e} + \frac{2a - 1}{8}.$$

If the completed function contains an explicit pole-removing factor, its pathwise argument contribution is added separately after division by π . This gives the displayed constant. In the two cases treated here, the only such factor is $\frac{1}{2}s(s-1)$ in $\xi(s)$, whose contribution is Lemma 3.3; beta has no pole-removing factor. \square

These individual calculations generalize to a single structural expression for any primitive Dirichlet character.

Theorem 3.7 (General Dirichlet decomposition). *Let χ be a primitive Dirichlet character of conductor q and parity $\chi(-1) = (-1)^a$, with $a \in \{0, 1\}$. The gamma and pole contributions attached to the completed primitive Dirichlet factor give the constant*

$$c_\chi = \frac{2a - 1}{8} + \delta_{\chi, \text{prin}} = -\frac{\chi(-1)}{8} + \delta_{\chi, \text{prin}},$$

where $\delta_{\chi, \text{prin}} = 1$ if χ is the principal primitive character and 0 otherwise.

Proof. The gamma-conductor factor of a primitive Dirichlet L -function has the form $G_{q,a}(s)$, so Proposition 3.2 gives gamma-factor contribution $(2a - 1)/8$. Since $\chi(-1) = (-1)^a$, this equals $-\chi(-1)/8$. A primitive nonprincipal Dirichlet L -function is entire and contributes no pole-removing factor. The only principal primitive character is the trivial character of conductor 1, whose L -function is $\zeta(s)$; Lemma 3.3 gives its pole-removing contribution $+1$. Adding these two contributions proves the formula. \square

This theorem establishes the structure at the contribution level. The three possible outcomes are:

- Principal primitive ($\chi(-1) = 1$): $-1/8 + 1 = 7/8$.
- Nonprincipal even ($\chi(-1) = 1$): $-1/8 + 0 = -1/8$.
- Nonprincipal odd ($\chi(-1) = -1$): $1/8 + 0 = 1/8$.

For the real zeta and beta cases, the lower-edge normalization fixed in Section 2 turns these algebraic contributions into the exact smooth constants of the upper-half main expression. While our immediate application is the

factorization of $\zeta_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}$ in Section 4, the theorem isolates the gamma-and-pole mechanism for every primitive Dirichlet character.

Remark 3.8 (Example: a nontrivial even character). The quadratic character modulo 5 is primitive, nonprincipal, and even, since $\chi_5(-1) = 1$. Thus $q = 5$, $a = 0$, and Theorem 3.7 gives the contribution-level constant

$$c_{\chi_5} = -\frac{1}{8}.$$

Equivalently, the gamma-conductor main expression attached to this character is

$$\frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{5T}{2\pi e} - \frac{1}{8}.$$

This example shows that the constant depends on parity, not on the numerical size of the conductor.

Specializing Theorem 3.7 to the Riemann zeta function and the Dirichlet beta function yields the baseline constants for our analysis.

Corollary 3.9 (Zeta and beta smooth terms). *Write $M_F(T)$ for the smooth main term attached to F under the upper-half convention fixed in Section 2. For zeta and beta,*

$$M_\zeta(T) = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{T}{2\pi e} + \frac{7}{8},$$

and

$$M_\beta(T) = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{2T}{\pi e} + \frac{1}{8}.$$

Their constants decompose as follows:

$$\zeta (q = 1, a = 0): \text{ gamma } -1/8 + \text{ pole } 1 = 7/8,$$

$$\beta (q = 4, a = 1): \text{ gamma } 1/8 + \text{ pole } 0 = 1/8.$$

Proof. For zeta, the gamma-conductor part has $q = 1$ and $a = 0$, so the gamma-factor contribution is $-1/8$. Lemma 3.3 gives pole-removing contribution $+1$. Thus

$$-\frac{1}{8} + 1 = \frac{7}{8},$$

and the logarithmic term is $T/(2\pi) \log(T/(2\pi e))$. This agrees with the classical upper-half Riemann–von Mangoldt smooth main term for the zeta function [13, Section 4.17].

For beta, the character χ_{-4} has conductor $q = 4$ and parity $a = 1$. The completed beta function has no pole-removing factor, so $c_{\text{pole}} = 0$. Hence

$$\frac{2a - 1}{8} + c_{\text{pole}} = \frac{1}{8} + 0 = \frac{1}{8}.$$

The logarithmic term is

$$\frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{4T}{2\pi e} = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{2T}{\pi e}.$$

□

The beta main term in Corollary 3.9 is a strict upper-half specialization of the existing literature. Bennett et al. use the symmetric-height convention $|\gamma| \leq T$ for primitive Dirichlet L -functions [1, Section 2, equations (2.2)–(2.4)]. For χ_{-4} their smooth main term is

$$\frac{T}{\pi} \log \frac{2T}{\pi e} + \frac{1}{4}.$$

Because χ_{-4} is real, and because $\beta(x) > 0$ for $0 < x < 1$ by the alternating-series argument used in Lemma 2.3, no real critical-strip zero contributes to the symmetric count. The upper-half convention therefore gives exactly half of the symmetric-height smooth term:

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{T}{\pi} \log \frac{2T}{\pi e} + \frac{1}{4} \right) = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{2T}{\pi e} + \frac{1}{8}.$$

The beta formula above is therefore a convention conversion of the cited result. In the decomposition table, it occupies the odd real gamma row: the beta factor has gamma-factor contribution $+1/8$ and no pole-removing contribution.

The structural contrast between the two gamma-factor constants can also be seen before division by π . Let $\theta_\zeta(T) = \Theta_{1,0}(T)$ and $\theta_\beta(T) = \Theta_{4,1}(T)$ denote the corresponding gamma-conductor argument terms for zeta and beta, respectively. These terms use the same branch convention as above and omit the pole-removing factor and the argument of the underlying L -function. The preceding proposition gives

$$\theta_\zeta(T) = \frac{T}{2} \log \frac{T}{2\pi} - \frac{T}{2} - \frac{\pi}{8} + O(T^{-1})$$

and

$$\theta_\beta(T) = \frac{T}{2} \log \frac{2T}{\pi} - \frac{T}{2} + \frac{\pi}{8} + O(T^{-1}),$$

and therefore

$$\theta_\beta(T) - \theta_\zeta(T) = T \log 2 + \frac{\pi}{4} + O(T^{-1}).$$

The constant part $\pi/4$ is the argument-level form of the change from the zeta gamma-factor contribution $-1/8$ to the beta gamma-factor contribution $+1/8$.

Section 4 applies this decomposition directly to $\zeta_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}(s) = \zeta(s)\beta(s)$, where the gamma-factor contributions $-1/8$ and $+1/8$ cancel, while the zeta pole-removing contribution survives.

4. FACTORIZATION OVER THE GAUSSIAN INTEGERS

In Section 3 the constants $7/8$ and $1/8$ arose from a single mechanism: the gamma-factor contribution of each completed factor, together with the pole-removing factor carried by zeta. The Gaussian field is where that mechanism is exercised on a product. Since $\zeta_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}(s) = \zeta(s)\beta(s)$, the two smooth main terms add; the gamma-factor contributions $-1/8$ and $+1/8$ cancel, and the zeta pole-removing contribution $+1$ is the only surviving constant. This

section computes that product constant and confirms it against the standard completed Dedekind zeta function, for which the same value 1 follows from the signature $(r_1, r_2) = (0, 1)$.

The number-field constant. Although this section is organized around the Gaussian field, the same constant arises for every number field; we record the general statement first, and $\mathbb{Q}(i)$ returns below as the case where it meets the Dirichlet product.

Let K be a number field of discriminant D_K , degree

$$n = r_1 + 2r_2,$$

and signature (r_1, r_2) . The standard completed Dedekind factor is

$$\Lambda_K(s) = |D_K|^{s/2} \left(\pi^{-s/2} \Gamma(s/2) \right)^{r_1} \left((2\pi)^{-s} \Gamma(s) \right)^{r_2} \zeta_K(s).$$

This factor has simple poles at $s = 0$ and $s = 1$; the entire completion, whose critical-strip zeros are the nontrivial zeros of $\zeta_K(s)$, is $s(s-1)\Lambda_K(s)$, just as the factor $\frac{1}{2}s(s-1)$ makes $\xi(s)$ entire in Section 2. The discriminant factor contributes $(T/2) \log |D_K|$ to the argument at $s = 1/2 + iT$ and has no additive constant.

Proposition 4.1 (Archimedean and pole terms for number fields). *Let K be a number field of discriminant D_K , degree $n = r_1 + 2r_2$, and signature (r_1, r_2) . For the standard completed Dedekind factor above, the archimedean factors together with the pole-removing factor $s(s-1)$ give the smooth additive constant*

$$C_K = 1 - \frac{r_1}{8}.$$

The corresponding archimedean-and-pole main term is

$$M_K(T) = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \left(|D_K| \left(\frac{T}{2\pi e} \right)^n \right) + 1 - \frac{r_1}{8}.$$

For the standard completed Dedekind zeta function, this is the number-field instance of the usual gamma-factor main term for L -functions [6, Chapter 5]. The constant depends only on the number of real places: each real place contributes $-1/8$, each complex place contributes none, and the pole-removing factor contributes $+1$.

Proof. The proof separates the real archimedean factors, the complex archimedean factors, the discriminant factor, and the pole-removing factor.

Each real archimedean place contributes

$$\pi^{-s/2} \Gamma(s/2),$$

the same gamma shape as the zeta factor. Proposition 3.2 with $a = 0$ gives constant $-1/8$ for each real place, so the total real-place contribution is $-r_1/8$.

Each complex archimedean place contributes

$$(2\pi)^{-s} \Gamma(s).$$

By Lemma 3.1, applied with $\sigma = 1/2$ and $y = T$, the argument term for $\Gamma(1/2 + iT)$ is

$$T \log T - T + O(T^{-1}),$$

because the constant $(1/2 - 1/2)\pi/2$ vanishes. The factor $(2\pi)^{-s}$ contributes $-T \log(2\pi)$ and no constant. Hence

$$\arg((2\pi)^{-s}\Gamma(s)) = T \log T - T - T \log(2\pi) + O(T^{-1}) = T \log \frac{T}{2\pi e} + O(T^{-1}).$$

Thus a complex place contributes to the logarithmic main term but has constant term 0.

Finally, the completed Dedekind factor $\Lambda_K(s)$ has simple poles at $s = 1$ and $s = 0$. The pole at $s = 1$ comes from $\zeta_K(s)$. At $s = 0$, the archimedean gamma factors have total pole order $r_1 + r_2$. The standard special-value formula for Dedekind zeta functions gives

$$\text{ord}_{s=0} \zeta_K(s) = r_1 + r_2 - 1$$

[8, Chapter VII, Section 5]; in particular, $\zeta_K(0) \neq 0$ when $r_1 + r_2 = 1$. Thus in every case exactly one pole remains at $s = 0$, and the usual entire completed form is obtained, up to a positive normalization, by multiplying by $s(s-1)$. Since multiplication by a positive real constant does not change the argument, the upper-half branch used in Lemma 3.3 gives argument $+\pi$ for $s(s-1)$ at $s = 1/2 + iT$, where

$$s(s-1) = -\frac{1}{4} - T^2 < 0.$$

Hence the pole-removing factor contributes $+1$. Adding the real-place, complex-place, discriminant, and pole terms gives the stated constant and main term. \square

Remark 4.2 (Dedekind zero-counting estimates). Proposition 4.1 fixes the main term under the upper-half convention used here. Explicit zero-counting estimates for Dedekind zeta functions are given by Trudgian [14] and by Hasanalzade, Shen, and Wong [4]. When real zeros are included, the counting convention must specify the real-axis contour separately; the upper-half convention used here does not include them. For $K = \mathbb{Q}(i)$, however, no zeros are omitted: the real axis carries no critical-strip zeros of $\zeta_K = \zeta\beta$, since $\zeta(x) < 0$ and $\beta(x) > 0$ on $(0, 1)$ by the alternating-series argument of Lemma 2.3.

Table 1 lists the constant terms used in the zeta, beta, and $\mathbb{Q}(i)$ comparison. Gaussian product check. The Gaussian field is the one case where the Dirichlet description of Section 3 and the Dedekind description above meet: $\mathbb{Q}(i)$ is a number field, and its zeta function is also a product of Dirichlet L -functions. We compute the constant by both routes. For $K = \mathbb{Q}(i)$, $D_K = -4$ and signature $(0, 1)$, so Proposition 4.1 gives

$$M_K(T) = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \left(4 \left(\frac{T}{2\pi e} \right)^2 \right) + 1 = \frac{T}{\pi} \log \frac{T}{\pi e} + 1.$$

TABLE 1. Constant terms, after division by π , under the upper-half zero-counting convention. The real gamma rows are Proposition 3.2, the complex archimedean row is Proposition 4.1, and the pole-removing row is Lemma 3.3.

Factor	Constant (after division by π)
Even real gamma factor	$-1/8$
Odd real gamma factor	$+1/8$
Complex archimedean factor	0
Pole-removing factor	$+1$

The product route, carried out below, gives the same main term.

The Dedekind zeta function of the Gaussian integers factors as

$$\zeta_K(s) = \zeta(s)L(s, \chi_{-4}) = \zeta(s)\beta(s), \quad (1)$$

where χ_{-4} is the primitive real character modulo 4. This factorization is standard [2, 8]. The product completion and the Dedekind completion are related by the duplication formula for the gamma function [9, Equation (5.5.5)]:

$$\xi(s)\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4}) = 2s(s-1)\pi^{-s}\Gamma(s)\zeta_K(s),$$

in which the two real gamma factors of ξ and Λ combine into the single complex gamma factor $\Gamma(s)$ of Λ_K , and the remaining factor 2 is a positive real constant with no argument contribution. The two completions are therefore the same function up to this positive factor, so their argument variations — and hence the constant they produce — agree by this identity rather than by separate computation. On the product side this constant is the cancellation $-1/8 + 1/8 = 0$ of the two gamma-factor contributions; on the Dedekind side it is the constant 0 of the single complex place.

We keep the same zero-counting convention as in Section 2. Thus

$$N_K(T) = \#\{\rho : \zeta_K(\rho) = 0, 0 < \text{Im } \rho \leq T, 0 < \text{Re } \rho < 1\},$$

counting multiplicity and using the same right-continuous boundary convention as for $N_\zeta(T)$ and $N_\beta(T)$. Here $N_\zeta(T)$ means the count for the completed function $\xi(s)$, and $N_\beta(T)$ means the count for $\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$.

Lemma 4.3 (Product zero-count additivity). *If T is not the ordinate of a zero of either factor, then, with the preceding common convention,*

$$N_K(T) = N_\zeta(T) + N_\beta(T).$$

If ζ and β have a common zero, its multiplicity in ζ_K is the sum of its multiplicities in the two factors.

Proof. Equation (1) is an identity of meromorphic functions. In the critical strip the poles are absent, so the order of vanishing of ζ_K at a point ρ is

$$\text{ord}_\rho \zeta_K = \text{ord}_\rho \zeta + \text{ord}_\rho \beta.$$

Summing this equality over the same upper-half critical-strip region gives the displayed counting identity. Equivalently, away from zeros and poles,

$$\frac{\zeta'_K(s)}{\zeta_K(s)} = \frac{\zeta'(s)}{\zeta(s)} + \frac{\beta'(s)}{\beta(s)},$$

with residues adding at common zeros. The right-continuous value at a zero ordinate is obtained by the same limiting convention as in Section 2. \square

Corollary 4.4 (Product factorization for $\mathbb{Q}(i)$). *Let*

$$M_{\zeta\beta}(T) := M_\zeta(T) + M_\beta(T),$$

with M_ζ and M_β as in Corollary 3.9. Then

$$M_{\zeta\beta}(T) = M_K(T) = \frac{T}{\pi} \log \frac{T}{\pi e} + 1.$$

Proof. By Corollary 3.9,

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\zeta\beta}(T) &= M_\zeta(T) + M_\beta(T) \\ &= \left[\frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{T}{2\pi e} + \frac{7}{8} \right] + \left[\frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{2T}{\pi e} + \frac{1}{8} \right] \\ &= \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{T^2}{\pi^2 e^2} + 1 = \frac{T}{\pi} \log \frac{T}{\pi e} + 1. \end{aligned}$$

This is the value of $M_K(T)$ obtained above from the completed Dedekind zeta function for $K = \mathbb{Q}(i)$. \square

Thus the two effects combine cleanly. The logarithmic scales add,

$$\log \frac{T}{2\pi e} + \log \frac{2T}{\pi e} = 2 \log \frac{T}{\pi e},$$

the gamma-factor contributions $-1/8$ and $+1/8$ cancel, and the zeta pole-removing contribution $+1$ survives as the constant for the Gaussian field. Corollary 4.4 does not require the zero sets of ζ and β to be disjoint; multiplicities add by Lemma 4.3.

Imaginary quadratic fields. Having fixed the Gaussian constant by both routes, we record that the same cancellation holds across the imaginary quadratic family. Let K be an imaginary quadratic field with fundamental discriminant $D_K < 0$. Then

$$\zeta_K(s) = \zeta(s)L(s, \chi_{D_K}),$$

where χ_{D_K} is the primitive Kronecker character of conductor $|D_K|$. Since $D_K < 0$, this character is odd, so Proposition 3.2 with $q = |D_K|$ and $a = 1$ gives the logarithmic main term and Theorem 3.7 gives the constant $1/8$. Thus

$$M_{\chi_{D_K}}(T) = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{|D_K|T}{2\pi e} + \frac{1}{8},$$

and together with

$$M_\zeta(T) = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{T}{2\pi e} + \frac{7}{8},$$

we obtain the identity of main terms

$$\begin{aligned} M_\zeta(T) + M_{\chi_{D_K}}(T) &= \left(\frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{T}{2\pi e} + \frac{7}{8} \right) + \left(\frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{|D_K|T}{2\pi e} + \frac{1}{8} \right) \\ &= \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \left(|D_K| \left(\frac{T}{2\pi e} \right)^2 \right) + 1 = M_K(T). \end{aligned}$$

The gamma-factor contributions therefore cancel for every imaginary quadratic field, and $C_K = 1$ throughout the family; the Gaussian case $D_K = -4$, where $\chi_{D_K} = \chi_{-4}$ and $\zeta_K = \zeta\beta$, is the smallest instance.

The product completion is

$$\Xi_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}(s) := \xi(s)\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4}) = 2s(s-1)\Lambda_K(s).$$

Table 2 summarizes the constant terms in the product completion.

TABLE 2. Constant terms in the product completion $\Xi_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}(s) = \xi(s)\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$. The opposing gamma-factor constants cancel, and the zeta pole-removing contribution remains. The Dedekind route gives the same total because $\mathbb{Q}(i)$ has signature $(r_1, r_2) = (0, 1)$, giving $C_K = 1 - r_1/8 = 1$.

Term	$\xi(s)$	$\Lambda(s, \chi_{-4})$	$\Xi_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}(s)$
Gamma factor	-1/8	+1/8	0
Pole-removing factor	+1	0	+1
Total	7/8	1/8	1

Epstein reformulation. As a check on a differently-presented object, the square-lattice Epstein zeta function carries the same constant. Let

$$Z_{\mathbb{Z}^2}(s) = \sum_{(m,n) \neq (0,0)} (m^2 + n^2)^{-s}.$$

If $r(N)$ denotes the number of representations $N = m^2 + n^2$, with signs and order counted, then

$$r(N) = 4 \sum_{d|N} \chi_{-4}(d),$$

and hence, initially for $\text{Re } s > 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{\mathbb{Z}^2}(s) &= \sum_{N \geq 1} r(N)N^{-s} \\ &= 4 \sum_{N \geq 1} \left(\sum_{d|N} \chi_{-4}(d) \right) N^{-s} \\ &= 4\zeta(s)\beta(s) = 4\zeta_K(s). \end{aligned}$$

By meromorphic continuation, the identity holds on the common domain of continuation [3]. The constant factor 4 has no zeros and no argument

contribution, so $Z_{\mathbb{Z}^2}$ carries the same zero multiset and the same constant 1 as $\zeta_{\mathbb{Q}(i)}$, in a third standard presentation.

Numerical spot check. The preceding arguments determine the smooth constants; the numerical spot check below reports computed zero counts and signed residuals at finite height. Table 3 records $N_F(T)$ and

$$\Delta_F(T) = N_F(T) - M_F(T)$$

at four heights, where $M_\zeta(T)$, $M_\beta(T)$, and $M_K(T)$ are the main terms from Corollary 3.9 and Corollary 4.4. The identities

$$N_K = N_\zeta + N_\beta, \quad \Delta_K = \Delta_\zeta + \Delta_\beta$$

hold to the displayed precision, confirming the additivity of Lemma 4.3. The accompanying manifest records the computations against `mpmath` [7], `PARI/GP` [12], and the bundled `LMFDB` reference snapshot [11].

TABLE 3. Numerical spot check of product additivity and normalization consistency for the main terms from Corollaries 3.9 and 4.4. For each height T , the signed remainder is $\Delta_F(T) = N_F(T) - M_F(T)$, and the ratio $r_F(T) = |\Delta_F(T)|/B_F(T)$ measures $|\Delta_F|$ against the explicit zero-counting bound $B_F(T)$. Here B_ζ is the Hasanalizade–Shen–Wong bound [5] shifted by $7/8$ to match M_ζ , B_β is the halved symmetric Bennett et al. bound, whose main term already includes the beta constant, and $B_K = B_\zeta + B_\beta$. The largest displayed ratio is 0.201. The identities $N_K = N_\zeta + N_\beta$ and $\Delta_K = \Delta_\zeta + \Delta_\beta$ hold to the displayed precision, reflecting the product additivity of Lemma 4.3.

T	N_ζ	Δ_ζ	r_ζ	N_β	Δ_β	r_β	N_K	Δ_K	r_K
100	29	-0.0023	0.000	50	-0.3159	0.169	79	-0.3182	0.025
500	269	-0.5867	0.052	379	-0.1545	0.067	648	-0.7412	0.054
1000	649	+0.3838	0.033	868	-0.5018	0.201	1517	-0.1181	0.008
1500	1069	-0.2845	0.025	1399	-0.4879	0.188	2468	-0.7724	0.055

5. RESIDUAL NORMALIZATION

The exact constants of Sections 3 and 4 fix the origin against which finite-interval residuals are measured. Once the constant is pinned, the residual $N_F(T) - M_F(T)$ is referred to a common baseline across the functions treated here, whereas a constant wrong by δ shifts every windowed Fourier integral of the residual by an explicit, non-vanishing endpoint term. This section makes that dependence precise; it is the reason the additive constant had to be fixed exactly, and uniformly across the family, before any finite-interval residual analysis.

Let F be one of the zero-counting objects considered above, and let $M_F(T)$ be its chosen main term under the convention of this note. On a finite interval $[A, B]$, set

$$R_F(T) = N_F(T) - M_F(T),$$

where $N_F(T)$ uses the same right-continuous zero-counting convention as before. For a nonzero real Fourier parameter ω , define the normalized finite-interval Fourier integral

$$\mathcal{C}_\omega(F; A, B) = \frac{2}{B-A} \int_A^B R_F(T) e^{-i\omega T} dT.$$

In the explicit-formula setting for zeta and Dirichlet L -functions, arithmetic terms indexed by n carry the phase

$$n^{-iT} = e^{-iT \log n},$$

so the corresponding Fourier parameters are $\omega = \log n$ [2]. For $\mathbb{Q}(i)$ and the square-lattice Epstein zeta function, the product identities in Section 4 place the same parameters in the product description. The constant-shift calculation below is stated for arbitrary $\omega \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$.

Lemma 5.1 (Effect of a constant shift). *Let $A < B$, let $\omega \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, and let R_F and $\mathcal{C}_\omega(F; A, B)$ be defined as above. Suppose the main term is replaced by*

$$M_F^{(\delta)}(T) = M_F(T) + \delta,$$

where δ is constant in T . Let $\mathcal{C}_\omega^{(\delta)}(F; A, B)$ be the integral computed from $N_F(T) - M_F^{(\delta)}(T)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}_\omega^{(\delta)}(F; A, B) = \mathcal{C}_\omega(F; A, B) + \frac{2\delta}{i\omega(B-A)} (e^{-i\omega B} - e^{-i\omega A}).$$

Proof. Replacing $M_F(T)$ by $M_F(T) + \delta$ replaces the residual by $R_F(T) - \delta$. Therefore

$$\mathcal{C}_\omega^{(\delta)}(F; A, B) - \mathcal{C}_\omega(F; A, B) = -\frac{2\delta}{B-A} \int_A^B e^{-i\omega T} dT.$$

Since $\omega \neq 0$,

$$\int_A^B e^{-i\omega T} dT = \frac{e^{-i\omega A} - e^{-i\omega B}}{i\omega}.$$

Substitution gives the displayed formula. \square

Remark 5.2 (Normalization fixed by the additive constant). A constant shift of the main term changes the finite-interval Fourier integral by the endpoint term in Lemma 5.1. Thus the additive constants fixed in Sections 3 and 4, summarized in Table 1, fix the origin before such integrals are compared.

In the Gaussian case this normalization is compatible with both the product route and the Dedekind route: the zeta and beta gamma-factor constants cancel, and the zeta pole-removing contribution remains. With the origin fixed, the windowed integrals at the frequencies $\omega = \log n$ are referred

to a single explicit additive baseline, the point from which a closer analysis begins.

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AI-generated output was not treated as mathematical evidence, as an independent source, or as an authorial contribution. The mathematical direction, selection of claims, final definitions, arguments, computations, source files, and interpretation of the results are the author’s responsibility. No AI-generated references, numerical results, or mathematical claims were included without human checking against external sources, executable computations, or the manuscript’s stated definitions. The author bears sole responsibility for all claims, text, and conclusions.

Data and code availability. The numerical spot-check reproduction material is included in the `anc/repro/` directory of this submission. The Python generator is licensed under the MIT License. The generated output files in `anc/repro/outputs/` are distributed under CC-BY-4.0. The bundled LMFDB reference snapshot in `anc/repro/reference/` is LMFDB data made available by the LMFDB under CC-BY-SA. See `anc/LICENSE` and `anc/LICENSE-DATA`. The manifest records the runtime environment and the checks supporting Table 3.

Competing interests. The author declares no competing interests.

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